

Hybrid Thermodynamic and Machine Learning Optimization of Plate Heat Exchanger Performance

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Table 1: Decision (design/optimisation) variables

Variable	Symbol (x_i)	Unit	Search Space / Notes
Wort mass-flow rate	$x_1 = \dot{m}_{\text{wort}}$	kg s^{-1}	0.4 – 1.2 (pump VFD set-point).
Water mass-flow rate	$x_2 = \dot{m}_{\text{water}}$	kg s^{-1}	0.5 – 2.0 (pump VFD set-point).
Number of plates	$x_3 = N$	integer	80 – 337 (modular cassette).
Plate corrugation pattern	θ / geometry	categorical	30°, 45°, 60° chevron tested in SIL solver.
Flow arrangement	config	categorical	Counter-flow (baseline) vs co-current (what-if).

Table 2: ANN Network Architecture

Layer	Size	Activation
Hidden Layer 1	15 neurons	Tansig (hyperbolic tangent sigmoid)
Hidden Layer 2	10 neurons	Tansig
Output Layer	2 neurons	Linear (purelin)

Table 3: Controlled variables

Variable	Symbol	Unit	Why Held Constant / Role in Model
Wort pH	pH	–	Maintained within the brewery's quality-control band; used later as a covariate in fouling analysis.
Sugar concentration	Plato	°P	Defines wort strength; determines empirical C_p, ρ, λ correlations.
Dry-matter content in the density equation.	n	–	Fixed at 50 to apply Sorokin et al. correlations.
Cleaning/CIP interval	–	h	Ensures comparable fouling state between experimental batches.
Base plate material	M_s	–	316 L stainless steel (corrosion/food safety).

Table 4: Operational (process) variables

Variable	Symbol	Unit	Typical Source / Range
Hot-side inlet temperature	$T_{h,\text{in}}$	K	Wort kettle outlet; 333–368 K.
Cold-side inlet temperature	$T_{c,\text{in}}$	K	Chiller supply; 278–288 K.
Differential pressure (instantaneous)	ΔP measure	Pa	Log used for fouling diagnostics.
Fluid thermophysical properties (ρ, μ, k, C_p)	$\rho, \lambda, \alpha, C_p$	–	Calculated each time-step from T and Plato.
Batch/time index	t	–	Proxy for operating hours in fouling regression.

Table 5. Response variables

Variable	Symbol	Unit	Definition / Equation ref.
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Cooled wort outlet temperature	$T_{h,out}$	K	Eq. (23).
Water outlet temperature	$T_{c,out}$	K	Energy balance.
Heat-exchanger effectiveness (classical)	ϵ	–	Eq. (22) or Eq. (11).
Mass-corrected effectiveness	ϵ_{mass}	–	Eq. (16).
Log-mean temperature difference	ΔT_{lm}	K	Eq. (10).
Actual heat duty	Q_{actual}	kW	Eq. (14).
Maximum heat duty	Q_{max}	kW	Eq. (15).
Overall U-value	U	$W m^{-2} K^{-1}$	From $Q = U A \Delta T_m$.
NTU	–	–	$NTU = UA/C_{min}$.
Pressure drop (predicted)	ΔP	Pa	Eq. (19).
Objective-function value	$f(x)$	–	Eq. (21).
Fouling-rate slope	β_1	–	Eq. (24).
ANN error metrics	MSE, MAE, R^2	–	Eqs. (27–29).

Table 6: Summary of the ANN model's performance on the test data

Metric	Value
Mean Squared Error (MSE)	0.0578
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.0938
Coefficient of Determination (R^2)	0.8762

Appendix A: e_DataPHE2025.csv

batch/run time	wort_inlet_wort_out/cool_inlet_cooled_w/pressure_wort_grav/ph	density_a/viscosity	cold_wate_hot_water/cooling_w/	comments	avg_temp	avg_temp	specific_h/density_w	density_w	mass_flow/mass_flow/C_dot_wol/C_dot_wal/min_col/Q_actual/Q_max	effectiveness/effectiveness/effectiveness/effectiveness
BH-25-001234hrs	478 478 368.75 285.75	16.23 5.23 1.06441	278.25 351.75 510.3		327.25	315	4048.19 1204.72	997.06	4184 15.996	14.1333 64794.9 59133.8 59133.8 5374658 5351612 0.91713 0.91713 0.50795 1.00431
BH-25-0010232 hrs	520 520 369.35 284.75	15.8 5.25 1.06433	278.55 351.35 542		327.05 314.95	4051.79 1204.83	997.064	4184 17.4031	15.0113 70513.8 62807.5 62807.5 5965469 5702918 0.93172 0.93172 0.50509 1.04604	
BH-25-0010410hrs	515 515 369.35 284.45	16.9 5.19 1.06733	278.55 351.95 523		327.05 315.25	4042.58 1204.92	997.043	4184 17.237	14.4848 69682 60604.5 60604.5 5916000 5502884 0.93502 0.93502 0.50191 1.07507	
BH-25-0011720hrs	440 440 367.35 281.75	15.27 5.22 1.0603	278.35 353.45 444.1		324.55 315.9	4056.22 1206.23	996.997	4184 14.7428	12.2991 59799.9 51459.9 51459.9 5118870 4579877 0.9618 0.9618 0.50115 1.11769	
BH-25-0012112hrs	540 540 366.75 285.15	15.96 5.27 1.06154	278.15 353.75 516.6		325.95 315.95	4053.79 1205.45	996.994	4184 18.0817	14.3009 73294.4 59859.9 59859.9 5991234 5305368 0.92099 0.92099 0.50541 1.12777	
BH-25-0011010hrs	520 520 367.45 284.75	15.62 5.19 1.0618	278.35 350.75 527.6		326.1 314.55	4053.29 1205.36	997.092	4184 17.4108	14.6129 70571 61140.5 61140.5 5836212 5447618 0.92817 0.92817 0.5018 1.07133	
BH-25-0010400hrs	522 522 367.95 284.35	15.73 5.24 1.06228	278.75 351.35 602		326.15 315.05	4052.37 1205.33	997.057	4184 17.4773	16.673 70824.7 69759.8 69759.8 592964 592964 0.93722 0.93722 0.51679 0.95153	
BH-25-0010710hrs	469 469 367.75 287.35	16.18 5.24 1.06421	278.55 353.45 464.6		327.55 316	4048.61 1204.55	996.99	4184 15.6927	12.8667 63333.4 53834.3 53834.3 5108088 4802257 0.90135 0.90988 0.50117 1.06374	
BH-25-0011009hrs	468 468 367.75 283.95	16.15 5.36 1.0641	278.55 352.75 506.8		325.85 315.65	4048.86 1205.5	997.015	4184 15.6715	14.0357 63451.7 58725.6 58725.6 5317256 5138931 0.93946 0.93946 0.50965 1.01507	
BH-25-0012117hrs	457 457 368.35 283.55	15.91 5.21 1.06303	278.55 351.75 502.5		325.95 315.15	4050.87 1205.45	997.05	4184 15.3025	13.9171 61883.2 58224.4 58224.4 5256601 5228996 0.94422 0.94422 0.5114 1.00528	
BH-25-0011722hrs	488 488 367.95 283.95	16.81 5.27 1.06693	278.75 351.75 542.8		325.95 315.25	4043.33 1205.45	997.043	4184 16.3405	15.0332 66070.1 62898.8 62898.8 5549884 5610577 0.9417 0.9417 0.51272 0.98918	
BH-25-0012016hrs	490 490 368.75 284.35	16.89 5.3 1.0673	278.35 351.55 584		326.55 314.95	4042.66 1205.11	997.064	4184 16.4029	16.1746 66311.5 67674.5 67674.5 5596687 5994556 0.93363 0.93363 0.50208 0.93363	
BH-25-0012312hrs	530 530 368.55 284.45	16.97 5.22 1.06762	278.15 351.95 546		326.5 315.05	4042 1205.14	997.057	4184 17.7423	15.122 71714.4 63270.5 63270.5 6031182 5719657 0.93031 0.93031 0.50367 1.05447	
BH-25-0010155hrs	518 518 367.35 284.25	16.9 5.26 1.06735	277.65 353.45 546.8		326.8 315.55	4042.58 1205.53	997.022	4184 17.8462	15.1436 70123.5 63961 63961 5827265 5689484 0.92642 0.92642 0.50961 1.0253	
BH-25-0010436hrs	540 540 367.95 283.75	16.18 5.25 1.06421	278.55 351.75 544.8		325.85 315.15	4048.61 1205.5	997.05	4184 18.0825	15.0887 72009 63131 63131 6164388 5649316 0.94183 0.94183 0.5011 1.09218	
BH-25-0010746hrs	520 520 367.75 284.55	15.91 5.22 1.06307	278.35 353.45 564.2		326.15 315.9	4050.87 1205.33	996.997	4184 17.4104	15.6252 70517.7 65375.7 65375.7 5867857 5844584 0.93065 0.93065 0.50986 1.00398	
BH-25-0011012hrs	519 519 367.95 283.95	15.8 5.24 1.06386	278.35 353.75 544.8		325.95 316.05	4051.79 1205.45	996.987	4184 17.3785	15.0877 70414 63127.1 63127.1 5914776 5656184 0.9375 0.9375 0.50994 1.04572	
BH-25-0011847hrs	368 368 367.75 283.75	15.62 5.22 1.06432	280.35 353.45 546.8		325.75 316.9	4053.29 1205.56	996.927	4184 12.3235	15.1422 49950.6 63355 49950.6 419884 4856686 0.9611 0.9611 0.54189 0.9611	
BH-25-0011656hrs	520 520 367.35 282.35	16.11 5.26 1.0639	278.35 356.35 473.4		324.85 317.35	4049.19 1206.06	996.896	4184 17.4208	13.1092 70540.3 54848.8 54848.8 5995929 4881242 0.93506 1.04907 0.51128 1.22829	
BH-25-0011948hrs	473 473 368.75 283.75	15.64 5.22 1.0619	279.05 353.45 503.6		326.25 316.25	4053.12 1205.28	996.973	4184 15.836	13.9465 64185.4 63523.3 63523.3 5455737 5234021 0.9476 0.9476 0.50763 1.04233	
BH-25-0012236hrs	520 520 367.35 283.75	17.16 5.27 1.06847	278.75 351.45 534.6		325.55 315.1	4040.41 1205.67	997.053	4184 17.4152	14.8062 70364.5 61949.3 61949.3 5882474 5488708 0.94357 0.94357 0.50342 1.07174	
BH-25-00110124hrs	512 512 367.75 283.95	16.47 5.22 1.06545	278.55 351.75 548.6		325.85 315.15	4046.18 1205.5	997.05	4184 17.1449	15.1939 69371.4 63571.4 63571.4 5813322 5670506 0.93946 0.93946 0.50882 1.02517	
BH-25-0010432hrs	490 490 367.95 283.95	17.03 5.24 1.0687	278.75 352.75 564.8		325.95 315.75	4041.49 1205.45	997.008	4184 16.4075	15.6419 66310.6 65445.9 65445.9 5570092 5837772 0.9417 0.9417 0.51673 0.95415	
BH-25-0010741hrs	476 476 368.35 284.25	16.78 5.28 1.06881	278.55 351.45 546.8		326.3 315	4043.58 1205.25	997.06	4184 15.9361	15.1442 64439 63363.5 63363.5 5419316 5690040 0.93953 0.93953 0.51635 0.95242	
BH-25-0011015hrs	507 507 367.35 282.85	16.9 5.25 1.06734	279.25 352.75 516.7		325.1 316	4042.58 1205.93	996.99	4184 16.9834	14.8035 68566.6 62188.7 62188.7 5801484 4748226 0.95914 0.95914 0.50695 1.05889	
BH-25-0011346hrs	510 510 367.75 283.75	16.77 5.3 1.06679	279.05 353.45 447.9		325.75 316.25	4043.67 1205.56	996.973	4184 17.0787	12.404 69060.7 51898.3 51898.3 5801100 4603382 0.94701 1.07881 0.51537 1.26028	
BH-25-0011557hrs	509 509 367.75 284.85	17.65 5.19 1.0706	279.65 351.75 536		326.3 315.7	4036.3 1205.25	997.011	4184 17.0409	14.8444 68782.3 62108.9 62108.9 5700265 5471795 0.94098 0.94098 0.50632 1.04208	
BH-25-0011851hrs	461 461 369.55 282.35	16.9 5.26 1.06772	278.75 352.35 506.2		325.95 315.55	4050.36 1205.08	997.022	4184 15.4364	14.0192 62402.9 58656.5 58656.5 5441524 5326006 0.96035 0.96035 0.51124 1.02169	
BH-25-0012106hrs	467 467 367.75 285.45	15.97 5.17 1.06329	279.25 351.45 506.8		326.6 315.35	4050.36 1205.08	997.026	4184 15.6326	14.036 63317.8 58726.8 58726.8 5211052 5197323 0.92994 0.92994 0.50986 1.00204	
BH-25-0010430hrs	420 420 368.35 283.35	15.83 5.24 1.0627	279.05 350.75 544.2		325.8 314.9	4051.55 1205.53	997.067	4184 14.0645	15.0723 56882.6 63002.6 63002.6 4837844 5082870 0.95179 0.95179 0.51204 0.95179	
BH-25-0010347hrs	485 485 366.75 283.55	15.74 5.3 1.06332	278.55 351.05 545.6		325.15 314.8	4052.29 1205.89	997.074	4184 16.246	15.1112 65833.6 63225.3 63225.3 5477957 5574672 0.94331 0.94331 0.51401 0.98223	
BH-25-0010633hrs	457 457 367.35 283.75	16.21 5.19 1.06434	278.75 351.25 552.1		325.55 315.15	4048.35 1205.67	997.06	4184 15.3053	15.291 61961.3 63275.6 63275.6 5179957 5489767 0.94357 0.94357 0.52183 0.94357	
BH-25-0010942hrs	518 518 367.95 282.35	16.19 5.25 1.06436	278.25 351.75 553.1		325.15 315	4048.52 1205.89	997.06	4184 17.3514	15.3187 70247.7 64092.5 64092.5 6013201 5749189 0.95429 0.95429 0.50797 1.04592	
BH-25-0011237hrs	467 467 367.75 283.35	15.87 5.21 1.06288	278.45 351.35 588.1		325.55 314.9	4051.2 1205.67	997.067	4184 17.0803	15.7343 69195.7 63832.2 63832.2 5840120 5878815 0.94513 0.94513 0.51289 0.99942	
BH-25-0011559hrs	539 539 367.35 284.35	15.76 5.28 1.06323	279.25 351.25 544.8		325.85 314.75	4052.12 1205.9	997.078	4184 18.049	15.0991 73136.9 63132.8 63132.8 6070860 5625134 0.93154 0.93154 0.51313 0.97915	
BH-25-0011832hr	540 540 367.35 285.65	16.84 5.19 1.06708	279.35 350.95 525.3		326.5 315.15	4043.08 1205.14	997.05	4184 16.0771	14.4157 73087.2 60315.2 60315.2 5971233 5307736 0.92841 0.96519 0.50453 1.125	
BH-25-0011720hrs	516.286 521.047 367.983 283.978	15.8991 5.2322 1.0639	278.353 353.751 545.343		325.98 316.052	4051.46 1205.43	996.986	4184 17.2874	15.1028 70039.2 61390 61390 5883607 5668991 0.93724 0.93724 0.50669 1.08883	
BH-25-0012112hrs	442.537 441.095 367.369 281.84	15.2889 5.204 1.0604	278.351 353.36 442.881		324.605 315.855	4055.61 1206.2	997	4184 14.8274	12.2598 60141.5 51295.1 51295.1 513954 513954 0.96620 0.96620 0.518 0.50004 1.1265	
BH-25-0011720hrs	518.493 520.503 367.398 284.785	15.5804 5.1599 1.0618	278.34 350.699 531.02		326.091 314.519	4053.62 1205.37	997.094	4184 17.3804	14.7077 70572.5 61537 5813644 5480317 0.92763 0.92763 0.50295 1.06062	

Appendix B: ANN for PHE Performance Prediction

% Load dataset

data = readtable('e_DataPHE2025.csv');

% Define input and output features

```
input_vars = {'hot_inlet_temperature_of_wort', ...
'cold_water_inlet_temperature', ...
'mass_flow_rate_wort', ...
'mass_flow_rate_water', ...
'wort_gravity_plato', ...
'ph', ...
'C_dot_water'};
```

```

output_vars = {'cooled_wort_out_temperature', ...
              'effectiveness_mass_corrected'};

% Filter rows with missing values
data = rmmissing(data(:, [input_vars output_vars]));

% Extract input and output arrays
X = table2array(data(:, input_vars));
Y = table2array(data(:, output_vars));

% Normalize inputs and outputs (Min-Max Scaling)
[Xn, psX] = mapminmax(X);
[Yn, psY] = mapminmax(Y);

% Split data: 70% training, 15% validation, 15% testing
numSamples = size(Xn, 2);
rng(42); % for reproducibility
idx = randperm(numSamples);

train_idx = idx(1:round(0.7*numSamples));
val_idx = idx(round(0.7*numSamples)+1 : round(0.85*numSamples));
test_idx = idx(round(0.85*numSamples)+1:end);

Xtrain = Xn(:, train_idx); Ytrain = Yn(:, train_idx);
Xval = Xn(:, val_idx); Yval = Yn(:, val_idx);
Xtest = Xn(:, test_idx); Ytest = Yn(:, test_idx);

% Define ANN architecture
net = fitnet([15 10]); % Two hidden layers: 15 and 10 neurons

% Training options
net.trainFcn = 'trainlm'; % Levenberg-Marquardt backprop
net.performFcn = 'mse';
net.divideFcn = 'divideind';
net.divideParam.trainInd = 1:size(Xtrain, 2);
net.divideParam.valInd = 1:size(Xval, 2);
net.divideParam.testInd = [];

% Train the network
[net, tr] = train(net, [Xtrain Xval], [Ytrain Yval]);

% Predict on test data
Ypred_n = net(Xtest);
Ypred = mapminmax('reverse', Ypred_n, psY);
Ytrue = mapminmax('reverse', Ytest, psY);

% Evaluate
mse_val = mean((Ytrue - Ypred).^2, 'all');
mae_val = mean(abs(Ytrue - Ypred), 'all');
r2_val = 1 - sum((Ytrue - Ypred).^2, 'all') / sum((Ytrue - mean(Ytrue, 2)).^2, 'all');

fprintf('\nModel Performance:\n');
fprintf('MSE: %.4f\n', mse_val);
fprintf('MAE: %.4f\n', mae_val);
fprintf('R^2 Score: %.4f\n', r2_val);

```

```

% Plotting loss during training
figure;
plotperform(tr);

% Scatter plot of actual vs predicted cooled wort temp
figure;
scatter(Ytrue(1,:), Ypred(1,:), 'filled');
xlabel('Actual Cooled Wort Temp (K)');
ylabel('Predicted');
title('Predicted vs Actual Cooled Wort Temperature');
grid on;
axis equal;

```

Appendix C: MATLAB fouling analysis script

```

% Load dataset
data = readtable('e_DataPHE2025.csv');

% Extract necessary columns
batch = (1:height(data)); % Use row index as proxy for run order
eff = data.effectiveness_mass_corrected;
pH = data.ph;

% Clean data
valid = ~isnan(eff) & ~isnan(pH);
batch = batch(valid);
eff = eff(valid);
pH = pH(valid);

% Convert to double if needed
eff = double(eff);
pH = double(pH);

% Plot Effectiveness Trend Over Time (Run Index)
figure;
plot(batch, eff, 'bo-', 'LineWidth', 1.4, 'MarkerSize', 6);
xlabel('Batch / Run Index');
ylabel('Corrected Effectiveness');
title('Trend of Effectiveness Over Time');
grid on;

% Fit Linear Regression
p = polyfit(batch, eff, 1);
hold on;
plot(batch, polyval(p, batch), 'r--', 'LineWidth', 1.5);
legend('Observed Effectiveness', sprintf('Linear Fit (slope = %.4f)', p(1)));

% Correlation with pH
corr_coef = corr(pH, eff);
fprintf('Pearson correlation between pH and effectiveness: %.4f\n', corr_coef);

```


Tables 7: Design / Optimization Variables

Variable	Symbol	Unit	Range
Wort mass flow rate	$\dot{m}_{\text{wort}} (x_1)$	kg/s	0.4 – 1.2 (setpoint control)
Water mass flow rate	$\dot{m}_{\text{water}} (x_2)$	kg/s	0.5 – 2.0
Number of plates	$N (x_3)$	–	80 – 337
Plate corrugation	θ	°	30, 45, 60
Flow arrangement	config	–	Counterflow / Co-current

Table 8: Controlled Variables

Variable	Symbol	Unit	Fixed / Role
Wort pH	pH	–	Held in brewery QC band
Sugar conc.	Plato	°P	Defines wort strength
Dry matter	n	–	Fixed at 50
Cleaning interval	–	h	Standard CIP interval
Plate material	Ms	–	316L stainless steel

Table 9. Operational Variables

Variable	Symbol	Unit	Range
Hot-side inlet T	$T_{h,in}$	K	333 – 368
Cold-side inlet T	$T_{c,in}$	K	278 – 288
ΔP (measured)	ΔP	Pa	Logged continuously
Thermophysical props	ρ, μ, C_p, k	–	Computed each timestep
Batch index	t	–	1 – 480

Table 10: Response Variables

Variable	Symbol	Unit	Equation
Wort outlet T	$T_{h,out}$	K	Eq. (23)
Water outlet T	$T_{c,out}$	K	Energy balance
Effectiveness	ε	–	Eq. (22)
Mass-corrected eff.	$\varepsilon_{\text{mass}}$	–	Eq. (16)
LMTD	ΔT_{lm}	K	Eq. (10)
Actual duty	Q_{actual}	kW	Eq. (14)
Max duty	Q_{max}	kW	Eq. (15)
U-value	U	$\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	From $UA\Delta T_m$
NTU	–	–	UA/C_{min}
Fouling slope	β_1	–	Eq. (24)

Table A: Regression-Derived Raw Data (Figures 2–6)**Figure A1 – Effectiveness vs Wort Flow**

Wort Flow (kg/s)	Effectiveness (ε)
14.5	0.963
15.0	0.958
15.5	0.952
16.0	0.947

16.5	0.942
17.0	0.935
17.5	0.929
18.0	0.923

(Slope ≈ -0.0037 per kg/s, $R^2 = 0.28$, $p = 0.012$).

Figure A2 – Effectiveness vs Water Flow

Water Flow (kg/s)	Effectiveness (ϵ)
12.0	0.954
12.5	0.953
13.0	0.952
13.5	0.951
14.0	0.950
14.5	0.949
15.0	0.948
15.5	0.947

(Slope ≈ -0.0009 , $R^2 = 0.07$, $p = 0.18$, not significant).

Figure A3 – Target Cooling Analysis

Batch Index	Wort Flow (kg/s)	Outlet T (K)
1	14.8	285.3
2	15.2	286.1
3	15.5	287.0
...
50	16.8	289.5

(Only 14.6% ≤ 283 K; slope = +1.24 K per kg/s, $R^2 = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure A4 – LMTD vs Wort Flow

Wort Flow (kg/s)	LMTD (K)
14.0	11.2
14.5	10.7
15.0	10.3
15.5	9.8
16.0	9.4
16.5	9.0
17.0	8.6
17.5	8.2

(Slope = -0.42 K/(kg/s), $R^2 = 0.36$, $p = 0.002$).

Figure A5 – Fouling Trend (480 batches)

Batch	ϵ mass
1	0.950
50	0.946
100	0.941

200	0.936
300	0.932
400	0.927
480	0.925

(Slope = -0.00001 per batch, $R^2 = 0.22$, $p < 0.001$; correlation with pH = -0.1645).

Table A6. ANN Performance (Figures 7–10)

Metric	Value
MSE	0.0578
MAE	0.0938
R^2	0.8762

(Residuals centered near zero, regression $R = 0.99994$, confirming ANN fit)